

Network Research Data Support

The year 2023 in facts and figures

vu.nl/rds

The Network Research Data Support (NeRDS) helps researchers get support, services and solutions to manage their data and software to work in line with the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles. The NeRDS is the local digital competence center (LDCC) of Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam (VU) and consists of the RDM University Library services, faculty data management support services and IT data management and compute services. Here we will look back at some of the milestones and achievements made by the NeRDS in 2023.

User support

The RDM Support Desk is a central service of VU Amsterdam's University Library providing practical assistance, help and advice with RDM related questions. The monitor includes only the questions addressed to the ticketing system of the central RDM support desk. Questions to faculty data stewards or IT are not included in this monitor.

In 2023 the RDM Support Desk at the library received 1,202 calls, a growth of 64% over 2022. The main categories are questions about data management plans (DMPs), data processing and analyzing and the courses provided by the RDM team. Growth is seen especially in questions and requests on Yoda, Qualtrics and Research Drive. The number of questions on DMPs has grown significantly.

Support Desk calls per faculty 2022 - 2023

■ = 2022 ■ = 2023

Support Desk calls by category 2022 - 2023

■ = 2022 ■ = 2023

This corresponds with the growth of data management plans created by researchers. In the origin of the calls, there is an extensive growth from a small number of faculties and most of these questions are related to the usage of Yoda and the migration of Qualtrics towards a VU-wide solution.

Data Management Plans

With DMPonline researchers can write, share and download a data management plan. 2023 gave a tremendous increase of the number of DMPs created; 870 new DMPs in 2023 over 587 in 2022, a growth of 64%. The number of users also increased from 586 in 2022 to 805 in 2023. The overall number of data management plans created since the introduction of DMPonline is 2,514. The vast majority (80%) of DMPs are created using the VU templates for NWO and ZonMw grants. In 2023 information for the GDPR registry was added to these templates.

New Data Management plans 2018 - 2023

Awareness

From the growth in support calls and DMPs we see that researchers have become more aware of the importance of data management. Researchers are aware of the faculty and library support and can find support when necessary. This strong increase of support calls and DMPs created results in a high pressure on the support staff, as more questions need to be handled and more data management plans must be reviewed.

Training and workshops

The Network organized:

- 13 data management courses for PhDs with 180 participants (Writing a DMP)
- 3 Data Carpentries with 94 participants
- 7 software management trainings (Software Carpentries & Code Refinery) with 147 registrations
- 2 High Performance Research Computing (HPC) courses with 32 participants
- 2 Open Science Framework (OSF) trainings with 44 registrations
- 3 tailor-made data documentation workshops with 40 participants

NeRDS Community

The Network RDS is a community of researchers and research support staff within VU Amsterdam, who work with data and software management, exchange knowledge and experience on different aspects of research data and software management. The community consists of about 100 members and was using Slack as community platform for sharing knowledge. Early 2024 the community platform has been migrated to the NeRDS MS Teams environment. In 2023 the network organized

- 8 Data Steward Meetups for faculty and library data stewards
- 8 RDM community meetings for the network support staff
- 9 Data Conversations for support staff and researchers with 250 registrations
- 2 tailor-made training weeks for support staff (the Summer and Winter Training Days)

In 2023 we started a Monthly Programming Café, the Bytes & Bites events, for researchers to exchange experiences on programming and software management. 8 Programming Cafés were organized in 2023, with 200 participants.

RDM Information

RDM support website

Information on RDM support, services and solutions are described on two websites: the [RDS portal](#) as the general entrance to RDM information and the [RDM Libguide](#), covering detailed information and guidelines on data management.

In 2023 we introduced three instructive videos on data management:

- [RDM: How, what and why?](#)
- [Find out which RDM tool is suitable for your research project](#)
- [Yoda: How, what and why?](#)

Newsletter

In 2020 the RDS Newsletter was launched. It was restyled in 2023 and has been published 6 times in 2023, covering standard categories like an Agenda of events, a support staff member in the spotlight, and news on projects and services. You can sign up for the RDS Newsletter [here](#). The RDS Newsletter has 330 subscribers, the RDS social media account (X) has 570 followers (as of May 2024). In April 2024, a [LinkedIn](#) page was added to these channels of communication.

RDM tools

Store, publish and archive

In January 2023 we introduced Yoda as the preferred VU platform to save, manage and share research data in a cost-effective manner during and after a research project. Usage of Yoda is growing fast, in the number of users as well as in the number of datasets and volume of data stored.

- 301 users
- 9,7 TB of stored data
- 843 datasets published

A growing number of universities within the Netherlands are using or implementing Yoda. The VU is a member of the Yoda Consortium, being a core group of institutional users.

Next to Yoda, other RDM-solutions are recommended by the VU. **DataverseNL** is the platform to easily publish research data. **Research Drive** is recommended as a platform for easy storage and sharing of data with other researchers within or outside the VU. The **Open Science Framework (OSF)** is recommended for open data publication. And **Scistor** is the on-premise solution for storage and analyzing of large data volumes (storage volumes of Scistor are not depicted in the graph 'Data storage in TB'. The growth again is substantial, from 700 TB in 2021, to 863 TB in 2022 and 952 TB in 2023). The usage of all recommended research data storage and management solutions has increased in 2023.

To help researchers choose the most appropriate VU storage solution for their research data, in 2022 the [data storage finder](#) was introduced.

Qualtrics

This solution has become available in 2023 for all VU staff and students under a VU-wide license. A total of 1,471 users created 4,192 surveys with more than 200.000 responses with Qualtrics. The amount cannot be compared with previous years as 2023 is the first year for the VU-wide license. Until 2022 faculties used their own individual brands for Qualtrics.

Contact

For RDM information: www.vu.nl/rds - For RDM support calls: services.vu.nl - For the RDM support desk: rdm@vu.nl

Data storage in TB 2022 - 2023

datasets 2022 - 2023

users 2022 - 2023